

THERMO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 2.5D ANGLE-INTERLOCK WOVEN SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A multi-scale strategy is employed in the paper to investigate the thermo-mechanical properties of 2.5D angle-interlock woven shape memory polymer composites (SMPCs). The thermo-viscoelastic constitutive relationship of the yarn is described in the form of hereditary integral and the parameters of relaxation moduli are obtained from nonlinear fitting of Prony series based on the finite element results. The effects of warp and weft arranged densities on viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven SMPCs are studied in detail. It is shown that with the increase of warp arranged density the viscoelasticity in the warp direction decreases. With the increase of weft arranged density, the viscoelasticity in the warp direction first increases until it reaches a maximum and then decreases. The shape memory behavior along the warp direction in small strain region is also analyzed on the basis of the viscoelastic properties of the composites. The shape fixation ratio and the stress recovery ratio of 2.5D woven SMPCs can both be predicted from the relaxation parameters. The research in the paper lays a foundation for design and application of woven SMPCs in engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) have received much attention worldwide since 1980s due to their advantages, such as excellent shape recoverability, low density, easy controllability in shape memory behaviors, and especially, low cost [1]. However, the recovery force of SMPs is small when compared with that of shape memory alloys, and the recovery speed is also low. In order to achieve high recovery force and fast recovery speed, the research on SMPs has been extended to related composites [2]. With the rapid development of textile technology, woven fabric reinforced SMPCs (woven SMPCs for short) with superior delamination resistance and fairly good shape deformability have become the cutting edge in the field.

To date, some work has been conducted to analyze the thermo-mechanical behavior of woven SMPCs, mainly concentrated on shape recovery ratios and recovery stresses. Zhang et al. [3] studied the bending recovery behavior of woven SMPCs. The deformation recovery ratios were compared between pure SMP samples and the developed SMPCs. They also proposed an analytical model to predict the bending recovery ratio of the SMP based laminates, in which the woven fabric reinforcement was simplified as an isotropic material. Ahmad et al. [4] investigated the deterioration of mechanical properties of polystyrene-based woven SMPCs subjected to tensile loads. The results revealed that samples applied to strain within 100% showed good shape recovery ability while low recovery ratios were observed for samples extended beyond 100% owing to the delamination and broken fibers. Roh et al. [5] studied the recovery rate of woven SMPCs and established a new numerical model based on experimental data. Recently, the impact damage healing ability of SMPs has attracted much attention worldwide. Woven SMPCs with impact tolerance and self-healing ability have been studied. Nji and Li [6] carried out a series of experiments on 3D woven SMPCs to investigate the failure modes and evaluate its self-healing capability. It was shown that healing efficiency greatly depended on the impact energy.

It is worth noting that the matrix of woven SMPCs is shape memory polymer which makes it different from common woven composites. The existing models for SMPs basically fall into two basic categories: the models based on phase transition, proposed by Liu et al. [7] and the thermo-viscoelastic method firstly introduced by Tobushi et al. [8,9] and developed by Diani et al. [10].

In this paper, the multi-scale method is adopted to study the thermo-viscoelastic properties of one kind of woven textile reinforced shape memory polymer composites, named as 2.5D angle-interlock woven fabric reinforced shape memory polymer composites (2.5D woven SMPCs for short). The micro-scale representative unit cell (RUC) of the yarn and the meso-RUC of the woven composites are established. Viscoelastic parameters of the yarn are also derived in the paper. The influence of weaving densities on viscoelasticity is investigated in the paper and the shape memory behavior of 2.5D woven SMPCs is studied based on the viscoelastic properties.

2 MODELING OF 2.5D WOVEN SMPCS

2.5D angle-interlock woven composites of which weft yarns interlock with two layers of warp yarns in the thickness direction are considered in this paper. As illustrated in the photomicrographs of actual 2.5D woven composites, the cross section of warp yarns is close to rectangular shape while the configuration of weft yarns can be assumed as straight lines combined with quadric curves. Since the inner part accounts for the most part of the woven composites, only the interior cell is studied in this paper. To establish the finite element model of 2.5D woven SMPCs, several assumptions are made as follows: (1) weft yarns and warp yarns have the same cross-sectional area which keeps unchanged along their tracks; (2) weft yarns are straight while the track of warp yarns are assumed to be straight lines combined with quadric curves; (3) the heights of the cross-section of all the yarns are the same.

Figure 1: The geometric relation in the RUC of 2.5D woven SMPCs.

The idealized model of the RUC is shown in Figure 1. The longitudinal and transverse lengths, L_x and L_y , can be obtained from the woven parameters.

$$L_x = (10 / N_t) \times 2 \quad L_y = (10 / N_p) \times 2 \quad (1)$$

where N_t and N_p are the warp and weft arranged densities (*tows/cm*), respectively.

The cross-sectional size of the yarn can be calculated from the equation below

$$A = \frac{T}{1000\rho P} \quad (2)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area of the yarn, T is the linear density of the yarn, ρ is the material density and P is the packing factor of fibers in the yarn. The weft and warp yarns are both composed of glass fibers.

Some part of the outline of the weft yarn, from Point B to C , is assumed as a quadric curve which can be described as:

$$f = ax^2 + c \quad (3)$$

Thus the length b of the straight section of weft yarns, coefficients of the quadric curve, width of the weft yarn w_t , width of the warp yarn w_p and dip angle θ can all be obtained based on the assumptions above through the geometric relationships below.

$$-\tan \theta = 2a\left(\frac{w_t}{2} - b\right) \quad \tan \theta = \frac{L_z}{\frac{L_x}{2} - w_t - \frac{w_p}{\sin \theta}} \quad (4)$$

$$c = \frac{h_y}{2} \quad a\left(\frac{w_t}{2} - b\right)^2 + c = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$4\left(\int_0^{w_t/2-b} (ax^2 + c)dx + b\frac{h_y}{2}\right) = A \quad (6)$$

where L_z and h_y are the heights of the RUC and the yarn respectively, as illustrated in Figure 1. The finite element model of the RUC of 2.5D woven SMPCs is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Finite element model of 2.5D woven SMPCs ($N_t=6, N_p=11$).

3 THERMO-VISCOELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONSHIP OF THE YARN

Yarns can be considered as unidirectional fiber reinforced composites. Considering the uniformity of fiber distribution, a hexagonal model is used here to show the transverse isotropy. A rectangular micro-RUC, on which periodic boundary conditions can be easily applied, is adopted here as illustrated in Figure 3. The packing factor can be described by Equation 7.

$$P = \frac{2\pi r^2}{ab} \quad (7)$$

where $b = \sqrt{3}a$.

Figure 3: Micro-RUC model of the yarn.

The relaxation-type constitutive relationship of viscoelastic materials at constant temperature can be described in the form of hereditary integral as follows:

$$\sigma_i(t) = \int_0^t C_{ij}(t-\tau) \frac{d\varepsilon_j(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (8)$$

$$(i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6)$$

where $C_{ij}(t)$ is the relaxation modulus.

The viscoelastic behaviors of thermo-rheological materials follow the Time-Temperature Superposition Principle. The relationship of the relaxation modulus at certain temperature T and reference temperature T_0 can be described as

$$C_{ij}(T, t) = C_{ij}(T_0, \xi) \quad (9)$$

where $\xi = t/a_T$ is defined as reduced time from T to T_0 , and a_T is a function of temperature. If the temperature changes continuously with time, the reduced time should be expressed by the integral form

$$\xi = \int_0^t 1/a_T(T(\tau)) d\tau \quad (10)$$

The empirical WLF (Williams-Landel-Ferry) equation can be used to characterize the change of the shift factor a_T with temperature.

$$\log a_T = -\frac{C_1(T-T_0)}{C_2+T-T_0} \quad (11)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are positive constants depending on material properties.

Given the equations above, the viscoelastic constitutive relationship of the yarn can be written as

$$\sigma_i(t) = \int_0^t C_{ij}(T_0, \xi_1 - \xi_2) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} (\varepsilon_j(\tau) - \alpha_j(T(\tau) - T_0)) d\tau \quad (12)$$

$$(i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 6)$$

where α_j is the thermal expansion coefficient, $\xi_1 = \int_0^t 1/a_T(T(\tau')) d\tau'$ and $\xi_2 = \int_0^{\tau'} 1/a_T(T(\tau')) d\tau'$.

The relaxation modulus of the yarn can be expressed as

$$[C_{ij}(t)] = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11}(t) & C_{12}(t) & C_{13}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12}(t) & C_{11}(t) & C_{13}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13}(t) & C_{13}(t) & C_{33}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44}(t) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where all entities are relaxation functions of time. These functions can be derived by applying six simple loading cases on the micro-RUC model (uniaxial tensile loadings in three primary directions respectively and three pure shear loadings) with applied periodic boundary conditions.

Prony series are applied to fit the relaxation functions. Considering the small deformation, the elastic response of the yarn is assumed to be linear. Thus, the Prony series can be written as

$$f(t) = a + \sum b_i e^{-t/\tau_i} (i = 1, 2, 3, 4) \quad (14)$$

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven composites

In this section, the relaxation moduli of 2.5D woven SMPCs with different weft and warp arranged densities subjected to strains along X , Y and Z directions at 80 °C are investigated. In order to more

intuitively reflect the effects of weaving densities on the viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven SMPCs, the relaxation parameter R_I is defined as follows:

$$R_I = \frac{E_I(0) - E_I(\infty)}{E_I(0)} \quad (15)$$

where $E_I(0)$ and $E_I(\infty)$ represent the initial and asymptotic moduli along Direction I respectively. The value R_I directly reflects the magnitude of the viscoelastic effect of the woven composites in Direction I . Larger R_I corresponds to a stronger viscoelastic effect, and vice versa.

0.1% strain is applied in three principle directions to investigate the influence of weaving densities on 2.5D woven SMPCs.

Figure 4: Effects of warp arranged density on the relaxation moduli of 2.5D woven SMPCs at 80°C. (a) E_X (b) E_Y (c) E_Z .

Figure 5: Effects of weft arranged density on the relaxation moduli of 2.5D woven SMPCs at 80°C. (a) E_X (b) E_Y (c) E_Z .

Figure 4 shows effects of warp arranged density N_p on the relaxation moduli. It is obvious that E_X , E_Y and E_Z all increase with the increase of N_p and the effects on the modulus along Direction X is more apparent. Influences of the weft arranged density on relaxation moduli are also investigated and the results are presented in Figure 5. It is shown that the relaxation modulus along Direction Y increases with the increase of the weft arranged density, while the relaxation modulus in Direction X sharply decreases with the increase of N_t . With the same increment of weft arranged density, the increments of the relaxation modulus E_Y roughly remain unchanged since the weft yarns are major load-bearing part when the load is along Direction Y. The decrease of the relaxation modulus E_X is mainly due to the increase of the dip angle which would greatly reduce the load-carrying capacity along the warp direction. The way E_Z changes with N_t is a bit more complicated. With the increase of N_t , there is a small increment for initial modulus $E_Z(0)$ but a much greater decrease for asymptotic modulus $E_Z(\infty)$, thus the weft arranged density N_t would greatly influences the viscoelasticity of 2.5D woven SMPCs in Direction Z.

Figure 6: Effects of warp arranged density on viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven SMPCs.

Figure 7: Effects of weft arranged density on viscoelastic properties of 2.5D woven SMPCs.

As illustrated in Figures 4b and 5b, the relaxation effect in Direction Y is rather weak since weft yarns are almost straight. Thus only the relaxation effects in Directions X and Z are studied here. From Figures 6 and 7, with the same weft arranged density ($N_t=6$) R_x decreases with the increase of warp arranged density. With the given warp arranged density ($N_p=9$), R_x first increases until it reaches a maximum and then decreases. It is obvious that R_z decreases with the increase of N_p and increases with the increase of N_t . Moreover, the weaving densities have more significant influences on viscoelasticity of 2.5D woven SMPCs in thickness direction compared to the warp direction.

4.2 Shape memory behaviors of 2.5D woven composites

The shape memory behavior of 2.5D woven SMPCs is investigated on the basis of thermo-viscoelastic properties above. Considering the extremely weak relaxation effect in the weft direction, the in-plane shape memory function of 2.5D woven composites discussed in the paper can only be realized in the warp direction. Since a large bending deformation of a bar can be achieved with small stretch and compression strain in the warp direction, shape memory behaviors during thermo-mechanical cycles with small stretch strain in Direction X are studied in the paper. The corresponding procedure mainly consists of five steps. A pre-deformed tensile strain along Direction X is gradually applied to the meso-RUC at the rate of 1%/min at 60 °C (T_g+23 °C) in Step 1, and then the strain is fixed in Step 2 to finish the stress relaxation process. After that the whole model is cooled down at a constant rate (5 °C/min) to 30 °C in Step 3. The uniaxial tension is removed in the following step, and part of the pre-deformed strain is retained. In the last step of the thermo-mechanical cycle, the model is reheated to the initial temperature at 5 °C/min, being either (a) free of stress, or (b) constrained with the retained strain. The strain recovery process could be measured in the free-length recovery while the stress recovery could be recorded in the length-constrained recovery. A 3D temperature-strain-stress graph reflecting the two kinds of recovery procedures for 2.5D woven SMPCs ($N_p=9$, $N_t=6$) is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Temperature-strain-stress graph reflecting two typical kinds of thermo-mechanical cycles of 2.5D SMPCs ((a) free-length recovery, (b) length-constrained recovery).

The shape fixation ratio R_f can be defined as:

$$R_f = \frac{\varepsilon_{fix}}{\varepsilon_{pre}} \times 100\% \quad (16)$$

where ε_{pre} is the pre-deformed strain applied in Step 1 and ε_{fix} represents the retained strain at the end of Step 4 when the external force is removed, as illustrated in Figure 8.

Similarly, stress recovery ratio R_{rec} is defined as:

$$R_{cr} = \frac{\sigma_{rec}}{\sigma_{relax}} \times 100\% \quad (17)$$

where σ_{relax} is the equivalent stress after stress relaxation in Step 2 while σ_{rec} represents that after the stress recovery process at the end of Step 5 when the model is reheated to initial temperature with retained strain constrained.

As illustrated in Figure 8, the equivalent stress linearly increases with the strain when the model is stretched under high temperature. Stress relaxation is not obvious in Step 2 due to the low strain loading rate in the previous step. During the stress-freezing process, the equivalent stress shows a gradually increase with the decrease of temperature. When the temperature is lower than T_g , the increasing rate of the equivalent stress remarkably increases since the relaxation rate of stress caused by thermal strain slows down rapidly. After removal of the external force, part of the pre-deformed strain springs back as a result of woven fabric reinforcement and thermal stress caused by cooling. In the free-length recovery process, the frozen strain is gradually released, and the shape recovery rate accelerates near T_g . The shape is completely restored to the initial state when the temperature is raised to 60 °C, and the shape recovery ratio is nearly 100%. During the length-constrained recovery process, the recovery stress after Step 5 is close to 10MPa, which is significantly higher than that of pure SMP (0.13MPa). It is favorable for its use as a driving device in the space deployable structures.

Figure 9: Shape fixation ratios versus pre-deformed strains.

Figure 9 is the summary of shape fixation ratios versus pre-deformed tensile strains with variations of warp or weft arranged densities. As shown in the figure, the influence degree of pre-deformed strain on shape fixation ratio decreases with the increase of warp arranged density and increases with the increase of weft arranged density. With the increase of pre-deformed strain, the proportion of thermal strain decreases, and the fixation ratio R_{fix} gradually approaches the relaxation parameter R_X . Thereby the influence of weaving densities on shape fixation ratio is consistent with that on the viscoelastic properties along the warp direction. This means R_{fix} decreases with the increase of warp arranged density, and first increases until it reaches a maximum and then decreases with the increase of weft arranged density. It can be deduced that when a relatively large pre-deformed strain or a bending deformation is applied to the model in the warp direction, the shape fixation ratio could be predicted with the relaxation parameter since the effect of thermal strain is negligible.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Thermo-mechanical properties of 2.5D woven angle-interlock shape memory polymer composites with different weaving densities are investigated in the paper. The thermo-viscoelastic constitutive

relationship of the yarn is described in the form of hereditary integral. The parameters of relaxation moduli are obtained by nonlinear fitting of Prony series and finite element analysis.

It is shown that the relaxation moduli in three principle directions of woven composites increase with the increase of warp arranged density. With the increase of weft arranged density, the relaxation modulus in the warp direction decreases while the relaxation modulus in the weft direction increases. With the increase of warp arranged density, the viscoelasticity in the warp direction decreases. With the increase of weft arranged density, the viscoelasticity in the warp direction first increases until it reaches a maximum and then decreases. Furthermore, two typical kinds of thermo-mechanical cycles are simulated based on the viscoelastic properties to investigate the shape memory behaviors of 2.5D woven SMPCs. The shape memory effects of SMPs or SMPCs are essentially due to the variation of viscoelastic properties as the temperature changes, and the shape fixation ratio and the stress recovery ratio can both be predicted from the relaxation parameters. The study in the paper proposes a feasible approach for further investigation of 2.5 woven SMPCs, and lays a foundation for their design and application in engineering.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Leng, J.; Xin, L.; Liu, Y.; Du, S. Shape-memory polymers and their composites: Stimulus methods and applications. *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 2011, 56, 1077-1135.
- [2] Leng, J.; Lu, H.; Liu, Y.; Huang, W.M.; Du, S. Shape-Memory Polymers—A Class of Novel Smart Materials. *Mrs Bulletin* 2009, 34, 848-855.
- [3] Zhang, C. S.; Ni Q. Q. Bending behavior of shape memory polymer based laminates. *Compos. Struct.* 2007, 78, 153-161.
- [4] Ahmad, M.; Singh, D.; Fu, Y. Q.; MirafTAB, M.; Luo, J. K. Stability and deterioration of a shape memory polymer fabric composite under thermomechanical stress. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 2011, 96, 1470-1477.
- [5] Roh, J. H.; Kim, H. J.; Bae, J. S. Shape memory polymer composites with woven fabric reinforcement for self-deployable booms. *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 2014, 25, 2256-2266.
- [6] Nji, J.; Li, G. A self-healing 3D woven fabric reinforced shape memory polymer composite for impact mitigation. *Smart Mater. Struct.* 2010, 19, 35007-35015(9).
- [7] Liu, Y.; Gall, K.; Dunn, M. L.; Greenberg, A. R.; Diani, J. Thermomechanics of shape memory polymers: Uniaxial experiments and constitutive modeling, *Int. J. Plast.* 2006, 22, 279-313.
- [8] Tobushi, H.; Hashimoto, T.; Hayashi, S.; Yamada, E. Thermomechanical Constitutive Modeling in Shape Memory Polymer of Polyurethane Series. *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 1997, 8, 711-718.
- [9] Tobushi, H.; Okumura, K.; Hayashi, S.; Ito, N. Thermomechanical constitutive model of shape memory polymer. *Mech. Mater.* 2001, 33, 545-554.
- [10] Diani, J.; Liu, Y.; Gall, K. Finite strain 3D thermoviscoelastic constitutive model for shape memory polymers. *Polym. Eng. Sci.* 2006, 46, 486-492.